

Physicochemical Studies of Complexes of Transition Metal Ions with *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic Acid

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Complex formation studies of hydroxamic acids with several metal ions in solution have been undertaken by various workers¹. However, not much attention has been paid to the structural studies of solid complexes of hydroxamic acids with transition metal ions. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid (PBHA) has been explored as a potential bidentate analytical reagent for large number of metal ions². Although some work has been done by earlier workers³ on *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid and its solid complexes with metal ions, not much attention has been paid to the structural studies of these complexes. The present communication describes the chelating ability and tentative geometry of *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid with some transition metal ions of first transition series on the basis of elemental, conductance, thermal analysis, magnetic and spectral (electronic, infrared) data.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data of the complexes are reported in Table 1. Molar conductance values of the complexes in nitrobenzene were found to be in the range 2–15 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ which is close to that reported for nonelectrolytes⁴.

Infrared spectra: The assignment of the ir bands have been made in Table 2 on the basis of literature data⁵. As anticipated, a broad band around 3 100 cm^{-1} , assigned to hydrogen bonded OH stretching for the ligand (PBHA), disappears in the spectra of all the complexes indicating that proton of the OH group is replaced by the metal ion upon chelation. The band due to C=O stretching vibration in the free ligand (1 630 cm^{-1}) is displaced towards lower frequency in the metal complexes (1 580–1 590 cm^{-1}) to more or less the same extent. The C–N stretching frequency in the free ligand (1 395 cm^{-1}) is found to be displaced to higher frequency (1 420–1 440 cm^{-1}) on complex formation. Such lowering of C=O frequencies and increase of C–N frequencies indicate that coordination of hydroxamic acid occurs through oxygen of carbonyl group. The band due to N–O stretching vibration in free ligand (910 cm^{-1}) gets shifted to higher frequency side (925–935 cm^{-1}) on complexation. Metal-oxygen stretching vibration assignments are arrived at on the basis of the data available in the literature⁵ by observing stretching frequency between 460 to 615 cm^{-1} . All the metal complexes of the PBHA show metal-oxygen stretching vibration in the range 575–585 cm^{-1} . The presence of a M=O bond can be correlated⁶

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.
		Metal	N	C	H	
TiO(PBHA) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Yellow	10.00 (9.47)	5.28 (5.33)	60.85 (61.67)	4.22 (4.35)	Dia
VO(OH)(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Violet black	10.08 (9.36)	4.85 (5.15)	56.51 (57.36)	4.46 (4.60)	Dia
CrO ₂ (PBHA) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Yellow	9.39 (9.88)	4.97 (5.32)	58.69 (59.31)	4.29 (4.18)	Dia
Mn(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Greenish yellow	10.52 (10.67)	5.04 (5.44)	61.04 (60.59)	4.36 (4.66)	5.75
Fe ^{II} (PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Dark red	10.59 (10.83)	5.76 (5.43)	61.79 (60.48)	4.38 (4.65)	5.20
Fe ^{III} (PBHA) ₂ ·5H ₂ O	Brick red	7.65 (7.14)	5.02 (5.37)	59.80 (59.86)	4.83 (5.12)	5.80
Co(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Pink	10.99 (11.36)	5.01 (5.39)	61.00 (60.12)	4.46 (4.62)	4.25
Ni(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Light green	11.06 (11.32)	5.65 (5.40)	61.04 (60.15)	4.36 (4.63)	3.83
Cu(PBHA) ₂	Green	12.95 (13.03)	5.35 (5.74)	63.49 (63.99)	4.10 (4.10)	2.00
Zn(PBHA) ₂	White	13.01 (13.36)	5.61 (5.72)	63.50 (63.75)	4.30 (4.09)	Dia
MoO ₃ (PBHA) ₂	Light green	18.00 (17.38)	4.80 (5.07)	55.98 (56.53)	3.70 (3.62)	Dia
UO ₂ (PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Dark red	32.38 (32.60)	3.58 (3.83)	43.50 (42.74)	3.49 (3.29)	Dia

with a stretching frequency in the range 900–1100 cm⁻¹. Sharp absorption bands at 930, 995 and 1040 cm⁻¹ represent Cr=O, V=O and Ti=O stretching vibrations respectively⁶. The spectra of the compounds containing two M=O bonds per metal atom shows strong band⁷ around 1000 cm⁻¹. A sharp band at 1000 cm⁻¹ and a weak band at 820 cm⁻¹ are assignable to asym. O=U=O and sym. O=U=O frequencies respectively.

Magnetic properties: The number of unpaired electrons were found out from magnetic moment data (Table 1). The results give two different behaviours: (i) the complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^I, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were found to contain 5, 4, 5, 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electrons respectively showing paramagnetic behaviour and (ii) the complexes of Ti^{IV}, V^V, Cr^{VI}, Zn^{II}, Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} were found to contain no unpaired electrons showing diamagnetic behaviour. On the basis of literature data⁸, all the complexes except the Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes could be assigned to octahedral geometry. The Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found to be tetrahedral and square-planar respectively.

Reflectance spectra: The results of diffused reflectance spectra of the Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of PBHA are reported in Table 2 alongwith the absorption bands and tentative assignments. On the basis of literature data⁹ the complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} were found to be octahedral. The Cu^{II} complex was found to be square-planar.

On the basis of magnetic properties and literature data these complexes were found to be high-spin octahedral (*sp³d²*) except Zn^{II} for which tetrahedral (*sp³*) geometry is assigned.

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	λ_{max} nm	Assignments
Mn(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	430 730	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (G) C.T.
Fe ^{II} (PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	545 865	C.T. ⁴ T _{2g} → ⁶ E _g
Fe ^{III} (PBHA) ₂ ·5H ₂ O	540 640	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (G) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (G)
Co ^{II} (PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	480 530	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{1g}
Ni(PBHA) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	430 680	³ A _{2g} → ¹ T _{1g} (P) ³ A _{2g} → ¹ T _{1g} (F)
Cu(PBHA) ₂	420 620	² B _{1g} → ² E _g ² B _{1g} → ² B _{1g}

Thermogravimetric analysis: It is observed that water of hydration is eliminated at 70–290° which suggests the presence of water of hydration as coordination water as well as crystal one. According to Nikolaev *et al.*¹⁰, water eliminating below 150° can be considered as free crystal water and water eliminating above 150° may be due to its coordination to the metal ion. The complexes of Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mo^{VI} were found to contain no hydrated water. The complexes of the other metals were found to contain one or more water molecules in the form of either coordinated or crystal water.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The solvents were purified and dried whenever necessary. *N*-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the reported method¹¹. Freshly prepared phenylhydroxylamine and vacuum distilled benzoyl chloride in stoichiometric propor-

NOTES

tions were condensed in ice-cold ether solution containing aqueous suspension of sodium bicarbonate. The product was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. Solutions of the metal salts were prepared in distilled water and the ligand solution in ethanol.

Alcoholic solution of the ligand (10%) and aqueous solution of the metal salt were mixed in 2 : 1 (L : M) ratio (except 3 : 1 in case of the Fe^{III} chelate) and digested on a hot water-bath for ~0.5 h. The separated complexes were washed with hot water and water-ethanol mixture and dried.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy's method at room temperature. UV-visible and reflectance spectra were recorded on a Varian DMS 80 spectrophotometer and IR spectra using KBr pellet. Thermogravimetric curves were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 analyser with TADS computer system with a heating rate 10 min⁻¹. The conductivity measurements were made using a Toshniwal conductivity meter in nitrobenzene.

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